

APPLICATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS TO
TRACKED TRANSPORTATION SYSTEMS *

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Composite materials are being applied to many transportation vehicles, e.g., mass-transit cars, personal rapid-transit (PRT) cars, and freight cars. This paper reviews the structural design goals of these transportation vehicles and current applications of composite materials in production vehicles. The utilization of materials which are "advanced" for this sector of the transportation industry must be justified on the basis of life-cycle costs. This implies consideration of reduced braking and power requirements due to reductions in weight, reduced maintenance, and improved durability. However, other important design goals require innovative approaches to structural configurations and these include acquisition cost reduction, vandalism resistance, fire retardance, and smoke suppression.

The industrial designer, through styling and human factors, responds to the psychological and behavioral needs of the user and viewer of passenger vehicles. These designs frequently require large windows and slender pillars which provide opportunities for selective reinforcement of conventional materials with high modulus graphite fibers to obtain the required rigidity and crashworthiness. However, to effectively employ advanced materials systems, emerging processes, and innovative structural configurations, it is highly desirable to interact with the designers at the conceptual design phase of transportation systems, at which stage greater leverage exists to maximize the payoff of new technologies. The paper discusses the interaction of materials, fabrication processes, and design concepts and candidate structural design concepts are discussed for the carbody components of future personal and mass-transit vehicles using both plastic and metallic materials systems.

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